

FACTORS AFFECTING THE LEVEL OF HEALTH OF THE POPULATION

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ABSTRACT: The article covers important information about factors affecting the level of health of the population. Furthermore, significant rules of healthy life style and issues that obstacles human were given.

KEY WORDS: health, unscrupulous producers, healthy lifestyle, step-by-step, regularity, balanced nutrition, positive thinking.

Everybody wants good health, because it ensures the harmonious development of the personality, determines the ability to work and is the main human need. And, unfortunately, not everyone is familiar with the factors, determining health. People often shift responsibility to others, not caring about themselves. Leading a bad lifestyle, by the age of thirty, the body is in an awful state and only then think about medicine. The way of life is that you are. That's right, because the right food, jogging, charging, cold shower, hardening is your health. You must be able to deny yourself good. Let's say that friends call for a nightclub, and tomorrow a hard day ahead, of course, it's better to stay at home, to have a good sleep, rather than having a sore head, breathing nicotine, plunge into work. This applies to smoking, alcohol and drug use.

There are factors determining human health, not which depend on ourselves. This is the environment. Exhaust gases from transport, the use of goods and food from unscrupulous producers, mutating old viruses (influenza) and the emergence of new ones - all this negatively affects our health. We are also dependent on the health care system, existing in the region in which we live. Medicine in many cases is paid, and not many have the means to get the help of a good, highly qualified specialist[1]. Thus, we have defined health as a value and the factors that determine it have been considered. Health is a diamond that requires cutting. Let's consider two basic rules for building a healthy lifestyle:

1. step-by-step;
2. regularity;

It is very important in any training process, whether it is the development of muscles, hardening, stamping posture, mastering the teaching material or mastering a specialty, all to do gradually. And, of course, do not forget about the systematic, so as not to lose the result, experience and skills[2]. So, we considered the main factors determining health, and now we will talk about processes that negatively affect the way of life of a person. It should be noted that maintaining a healthy imagelife is not just a sporting activity, adherence to regimes and proper nutrition. This is a certain attitude that a person adheres to. He is engaged in self-improvement, spiritual development, increases the cultural level. Everything in the aggregate makes his life better. Lifestyle is the first major factor. A prudent human behavior aimed at maintaining one's health should include:

- observance of the optimal mode of work, sleep and rest;
- mandatory presence of daily physical activity, but within the limits of the norm, no less, no more;
- complete rejection of bad habits;
- only correct and balanced nutrition;
- teaching positive thinking.

It is necessary to understand, what exactly is the factor of a healthy imagelife provides an opportunity to function normally, carry out all social tasks, as well as labor, in the family and household sphere. It directly affects how much the individual lives[3]. By 50% the physical health of a person depends on his lifestyle, according to scientists. Another factor is environment. What factors determine human health, if we are talking about the environment? Depending on its effect, three groups are distinguished:

- Physical. This is the humidity of the air, pressure, solar radiation, etc.
- Biological. Can be useful and harmful. This includes viruses, fungi, plants and even domestic animals, bacteria.
- Chemical. Any chemical elements and compounds that are found everywhere: in the soil, in the walls of buildings, in food, in clothing. And also the electronics surrounding the person.

In sum, all these factors are about 20%,figure rather big. Only 10% of the health of the population is determined by the level of medical care, 20% - hereditary factors, and 50% are given a way of life. As you can see, the factors determining the statehuman health, a great variety. Therefore, it is extremely important not only to eliminate the emerging symptoms of disease and fight infections. It is necessary to influence all factors determining health. One is extremely difficult to change the environmentenvironment, but on forces to everyone to improve a microclimate of the habitation, carefully to choose food products, to use pure water, less to apply substances which negatively influence ecology[4]. Poverty has been recognized as a critical factor in the social determinants of health. Mikkonen and Raphael note in their 2010 monograph on the social determinants of health in Canada that, "Level of income shapes overall living conditions, affects psychological functioning, and influences health-related behaviours such as quality of diet, extent of physical activity, tobacco use, and excessive alcohol use." Community perceptions of safety are important. A community's perception of safety contributes to a sense of wellbeing, allows individuals freedom of movement, and reduces unintentional injuries. There are other elements of safety that impact on health. A Canadian research study shows a strong relationship between the commission of crimes and the use of alcohol and drugs.

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